

Lunar Prospecting and Scouting Rover – ConOps and breadboarding. Dr. Arthur Vangeffelen¹ (Thermo-Mechanical System Engineer), Hemanth K. Madakashira¹ (Team Lead – Future Projects and Exploration), Space Applications Services NV/SA¹ (Space Applications Services, Leuvensesteenweg 325, 1932 Sint-Stevens-Woluwe, Belgium). ²Dr. Jessica Flahaut, PhD (CRPG Nancy, France, jessica.flahaut@univ-lorraine.fr)

Introduction: The Lunar Prospecting and Scouting Rover (LPSR) represents a crucial milestone in Europe’s lunar exploration roadmap, aiming to deliver a medium-class rover (300–400 kg) to the Moon’s south pole by 2030. Surface mobility is a foundational capability for future lunar missions, enabling critical tasks such as environment mapping, prospecting, deployment and maintenance of surface assets, and logistics for human and robotic exploration. The LPSR mission objectives include achieving Europe’s first medium-class lunar rover deployment, advancing critical technologies to flight heritage, gaining operational experience in the challenging lunar environment, and guiding future mission designs and strategies.

LPSR’s nominal traverse approach employs a stop-go strategy, carefully tailored to the lunar terrain and slope constraints. Traverses on slopes below 10° allow speeds of up to 0.7 m/s, while steeper slopes (up to 20°) reduce speeds to 0.1 m/s to ensure safe mobility. As part of the stop-go approach, panoramic context imagery is captured every 50 m. In addition, every 100–200 m, the rover performs a slow traverse while operating a ground-penetrating radar (GPR) to characterize subsurface structures. At each science site, roughly every 500 m, the LPSR conducts two dedicated GPR mapping sessions to identify promising subsurface features. One of these areas is then selected for focused scientific activities, including high-resolution imaging, volatile sampling, and in situ analysis.

Breadboarding: The LPSR platform employs four flexible wheels mounted on an adjustable dual torsion-bar suspension with individual steering and traverse actuation. A modular breadboard model has been developed to reproduce the kinematic and dynamic behavior of the flight suspension while enabling systematic variation of stiffness and damping. A structured test campaign has been defined, combining static, dynamic, and reduced-gravity experiments to characterize stability margins, suspension kinematics, and dynamic load transfer across representative terrains, slopes, and velocities. The gravity offloading system enables testing at Earth, Moon, and Mars equivalent gravity levels without mass limitations, allowing direct extrapolation of breadboard results to multiple planetary environments.

The results provide experimental insight into suspension behavior under lunar-analogue conditions and establish a validated basis for future mission-level mobility system sizing and design.

Another aspect of the breadboarding also includes a vision-based GNC stack. Rover autonomy is tested at the LUNA facility. The results provide capabilities of GNC by determining maximum safe velocity, obstacle avoidance, and navigation performance under simulated lunar south pole lighting conditions.

References:

[1] BERNHARDT, H.; ROBINSON, M. S.; BOYD, A. K., 2022, Geomorphic map and science target identification on the Shackleton-de Gerlache ridge, *Icarus*, 379: 114963.

Figure 1. Hillshade and superimposed slope map with suggested traverse path (dotted, white line) [1]